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WP7 – ACCEPT demonstration activities

D7.13 – Demonstration activity report from the Dutch pilot site v1.0

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Table of Abbreviations and Acronyms

BIML	Building Information Management Layer
BoM	Bill of Materials
C-App	Citizen mobile application
CGI	Common Gateway Interface
COM	Commissioner
DC	Direct Current
DH	District Heating Plant
DHW	Domestic Hot Water
DR	Demand Response
DSO	Distribution System Operator
EC	Energy Community
EV	Electric Vehicle
HES	Home Energy Storage
HVAC	Heating, Ventilation and Air Conditioning
KPIs	Key Performance Indications
KPIs	Key Performance Indications
LEC	Local Energy Communities
P2P	Peer to peer
PD	Pilot Director
PV	Photovoltaic
REC	Renewable Energy Communities
TD	Technical Director
TEC	Technician
UC	Use Case

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable outlines the demonstration plan for the Dutch pilot site of the ACCEPT project, which aims to develop and test innovative energy solutions for local communities. The report provides an overview of the community's objectives, regulatory framework and the plan for demonstrating the use cases (UCs).

The deliverable begins by summarizing the Dutch pilot site's assets and the modifications to the UCs that will be tested compared to D6.7. It then details the pilot test-bed for the Dutch pilot site designed to test the various use cases identified to be suitable. The expected timeline is a first idea about the demonstration activities, because of the many uncertainties in the current stadium. A more realistic plan will be presented in version 2 of the deliverable.

Support activities will be provided to residents for installed meters in residential areas. This support will help residents understand how the equipment works and how to interpret the data provided by the meters.

Finally, the deliverable also outlines the next steps for the pilot site. The next course of action involves completing the installation and commissioning phase, resolving any remaining issues, and beginning the demonstration phase following the timeline outlined in the report. The aim is to implement the UCs successfully and demonstrate the effectiveness of the ACCEPT solution for sustainable energy solutions in local communities.

Overall, this deliverable provides a comprehensive report of the first part of the demonstration activities for the Dutch pilot site of the ACCEPT project.

1. Introduction

1.1. Objectives and Scope of the Deliverable

This deliverable presents the work conducted under Task 7.5 as of month 26 of ACCEPT project. This task aims to describe all the activities carried out for the demonstration of the ACCEPT solution at the Dutch pilot site.

The main objectives of the deliverable can be summarised as follows:

- Describe the Community, its objectives, as well as the regulatory framework and the constraints that affect the pilot site.
- Present the Use Cases to be tested in the Dutch pilot, introducing the Demonstration Plan for the activities to be performed for validation.
- Preparation of the test-bed for the ACCEPT solution operation, describing how the Uses Cases will be implemented.
- Describe the support activities to assure the proper data collection and the procedures to solve the issues that could arise during the demonstration period.
- Explain the foreseen actions to support and keep the engagement of the pilot participants.

The scope of this version of the report covers the works performed since the start of the task, month 20, until month 26. The expected timeline is a first idea about the demonstration activities, because of the many uncertainties in the current stadium. A more realistic plan will be presented in version 2 of the deliverable. The deliverable will be updated at month 33, with the first results of the demonstration activities. The outputs of these reports will be used to validate the ACCEPT solution, analyse the impact and explore the exploitation strategy.

1.2. Structure of the Deliverable

This deliverable is structured as follows:

- **Chapter 1:** Provides the main scope and objectives of Task 7.5 presents the structure of the report and the main section, and finally establishes the interdependencies with other tasks and deliverables.
- **Chapter 2:** Shows the Community objectives, presenting the ACCEPT Use Cases that will be tested in order to achieve the goals of the Pilot Site, as well as the regulatory framework and constraints that affect locally this Community. A description of the Demonstration Plan to be carried out for validation is presented.
- **Chapter 3:** Describes how to implement the different Use Cases and the activities that have been performed in order to get proper data from the IoT infrastructure deployed in the Pilot premises. Moreover, it explains the reasons behind the final Use Cases selected which differ from the ones included in D6.7.
- **Chapter 4:** Explains the procedures to follow when a problem is encountered due to a failure in the communication between ACCEPT server and the smart devices installed at the users' dwellings.
- **Chapter 5:** Offers information about the Dutch Local4Local project which can be seen as a continuation of ACCEPT to offer resembling services to all energy communities in the Netherlands.
- **Chapter 6:** Presents the next steps in the demonstration activities during the following seven months until the delivery of the second version of this report.

1.3. Interdependencies with Other Tasks and Deliverables

The main interdependencies of this Deliverable to Tasks and Deliverables of the same and other Work Packages can be summarized as:

D2.1: Use and Business Cases to be tested in each pilot site are described thoroughly in this deliverable. The responsible technical partners for each Use Case are also indicated.

D2.2: The Key Performance Indications (KPIs) and the datasheet for each KPI are detailed in this Deliverable.

D2.4: The system architecture description and a further description of the Use Cases is provided in this Deliverable.

D6.7: This Deliverable provides a detailed description of the validation scenarios which will be tested in the Dutch pilot site and is strongly connected to the Demonstration activity report.

WP8: This work package assesses the impact of the ACCEPT solution on the demonstration sites and analyse the results of the demonstration activities to elaborate the business plan and define the exploitation.

D9.5: This deliverable develops the replication roadmap and the plan for scaling-up of the solution based on the real pilot results.

The progress of this Deliverable is crucial for the whole progress and success of D7.13 v1.0.

2. Demonstration Plan

A first introduction to the deployment in the ACCEPT system in a controlled environment is given in D6.6. A more detailed description of the IoT infrastructure which could be installed in the pilot sites is provided in D6.1.

Compared to D6.1 a few basics changed. In the audits we found out at one hand it was not possible to implement all available assets and on the other hand HVAC-units are hardly available in our pilot site due to the colder climate. So we ended up with mainly the PV-installations and DHW installations such as boosters. This way all kinds of sensors were abolished from the project. Currently, we investigate the possibility to add BESS-systems to the households in the project.

Further to the hardware and software deployment in the Dutch pilot site and based on the validation scenarios of D6.7, the deliverable will include the specific demonstration plan with the local regulatory and community objectives and the preparation of the pilot test-bed for the ACCEPT solution operation.

2.1. Community objectives

ESR aims to establish a reliable, sustainable and payable energy system and uses ACCEPT to learn and overcome several difficulties and threads in the current energy system. The growing use of solar panels, electric heaters and heat pumps, but also vehicle charging unbalances the network. New behaviour and smart systems can probably help to reach a new balance in the system. On the pilot site we follow all energy streams (use case 1 Metering and sensor data) to get insights in the potential of changing behaviour of the system like storing energy surpluses (use case 2 Virtual Energy Storage optimisation) and demand steering by price triggers (UC4 Demand elasticity) on both individual level and at district level (UC12 optimal scheduling an operation of heating generation). UC 8 and 9 Participation in in demand response schemes will help citizens even more to behave in a way that is in favour of the community. The system should work in a way that also the district facilities like the heat pump and the PV park and charge facility are integrated.

Optimisation of network use is good for energy reliability, but also to keep energy payable it is important to match local demand with local supply; self-consumption within the community (UC 13 increase local self-consumption). All electricity that is not delivered to the grid help keep the network open and the cost low.

In our experience it is not easy to engage citizens in change towards a completely sustainable system. In Holland we're used to cheap abundant supply of energy at any moment. So energy supply by weather circumstances are not easy to accept. Therefore, we have to invest a lot in automation, back-up systems and communication. People should learn that we only can solve the problem in a social organisation with democratic processes and socialised costs. UC 14 active Citizen and LEC Engagement should help achieve that.

2.2. Local Regulatory Framework and Constraints

To make smart energy sharing possible, the new Dutch Electricity Act must be amended¹. First of all, energy sharing should be included in the law. Moreover, it is recommended to enable the prioritisation of projects that minimise the impact on the electricity system through

¹ <https://wetgevingskalender.overheid.nl/Regeling/WGK010483>

the use of flexibility tools, such as energy sharing. And rewarding electricity customers if they align their offtake with renewable generation over time.

Smart energy sharing by energy communities leads to:

- More involvement of citizens and thus more support for the energy transition²;
- Lower social costs of energy transition through better utilisation of electricity infrastructure capacity².

2.2.1. Clean Energy Package

Through the Clean Energy Package³, the European Commission wants to promote the active participation of consumers in the energy system. The Netherlands is implementing this package by:

- stimulating energy communities
- stimulating collective renewable production through a Cooperative Energy Production Subsidy Scheme
- a Development Fund for Energy Cooperatives
- aiming for 50% of production to be owned by the local environment (citizens and businesses)

2.2.2. Energy communities

Supported by this policy, in most towns and cities, energy communities are actively engaged in realising local, collective, and renewable production. In doing so, the energy communities are making a significant contribution to the energy transition, while at the same time, the members are becoming less financially dependent on the existing energy prices that are rising as a result of developments in the international gas market. The profits from their local production are then invested in other projects, such as collective heat projects or collective mobility.

2.2.3. Local use of flexibility tools

By deploying flexibility tools, more renewably produced electricity can be transported. This section discusses flexibility through demand response, storage, conversion, and electrification⁴.

Congestion can be avoided by purchasing sufficient local electricity at the same time as the local production of the electricity. Deliberately managing this is called demand response. With demand response, the generated electricity is purchased directly and as close as possible to the neighbourhood. In this way, the electricity can be transported over the shortest possible distance, via the cables between producers and consumers. In this way, the electricity consumed does not flow through the other cables and grid components in the sub-grid, or the transformers to an upper medium-voltage or high-voltage grid. As a result, congestion can be avoided.

² <https://energiesamen.blob.core.windows.net/media/Whitepaper%20Slim%20Energiedelen%20-%20Energie%20Samen.pdf>

³ https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/energy-strategy/clean-energy-all-europeans-package_en

⁴ https://energiesamen.nu/media/uploads/HandreikingSysteemintegratie_feb2021.pdf?_gl=1*1x8d7hj*_ga*MTg0MTM0MTY5Mi4xNjc2NTM2ODI5*_ga_7ZZS93YH5T*MTY3OTk5MDQzMy41NS4xLjE2Nzk5OTA1OTUuMC4wLjA.

Demand response is smartly driven by ICT. This smart control is necessary to give users a signal or a price incentive to buy more electricity or to switch on car charging or a neighbourhood battery⁵.

If local demand response possibilities are maximised, a remaining surplus of renewable electricity production can be stored in (car) batteries, converted to heat, or converted to gas. These are more expensive solutions than demand response. However, they will become increasingly cheaper in the coming years⁶.

2.2.4. Recommendations on legislation and regulations

To enable and stimulate smart energy sharing, we recommend the following five improvements in legislation and regulations.

1. Include energy sections in the Energy Act, in line with Articles 21 and 22 of Directive (EU) 2018/2001 and Article 16 of Directive (EU) 2019/944⁷.

2. Redefine the allocation point in the Energy Act⁸. Definition: the allocation point is a point in an installation whose energy value (delivery or feed-in) can be calculated unambiguously from one or more measurement points, and to which a single market party can be unambiguously linked. This makes it possible in the market model to 'share energy' alongside 'supply energy'.

3. When subsidising renewable electricity generation, give priority to projects that minimise the impact on the electricity system through the use of flexibility tools⁹.

4. Reward electricity customers with lower connection or transmission tariffs if they gear their purchase in an organised way over time to renewable production⁵.

5. When allocating transmission capacity, give priority to projects that minimise the impact on the electricity system by applying flexibility tools⁵.

2.3. Description of the Demonstration Plan

Although dynamic tariffs are not yet widely used in Holland, the ACCEPT project's objectives can still be fulfilled at the Dutch pilot site through simulated demonstrations, as it allows us to showcase the benefits of the ACCEPT solution without the need for actual DR-events to take place. The Dutch pilot is engaged with the following Use cases mentioned in Table 1.

⁵ <https://www.rescoop.eu/uploads/rescoop/downloads/Flexibility-services-for-energy-cooperatives.pdf>

⁶ https://energiesamen.nu/media/uploads/HandreikingSysteemintegratie_feb2021.pdf?_gl=1*1x8d7hj*_ga*MTg0MTM0MTY5Mi4xNjc2NTM2ODI5*_ga_7ZZS93YH5T*MTY3OTk5MDQzMy41NS4xLjE2Nzk5OTA1OTUuMC4wLjA.

⁷ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32018L2001>

⁸ <https://wetgevingskalender.overheid.nl/Regeling/WGK010483>

⁹ <https://energiesamen.blob.core.windows.net/media/Whitepaper%20Slim%20Energiedelen%20-%20Energie%20Samen.pdf>

Table 1: Use Cases in the Dutch pilot with Key Performance indicators

ID	Name	Key performance indicators
UC1	Metering & Sensor Energy Data	SR-01, SR-02, SR-03
UC2	Virtual Energy Storage optimisation	EC-03, ER-04, ER-08
UC4	Demand elasticity profiling-forecasting-aggregation	AE-05, MR-01, MR-02
UC5	Intra-day district-level DER flexibility management	ER-01, ER-02, ER-03, ER-04, ER-05, MR-02
UC7	Community-level P2P flexibility	TBD
UC8	Participation in explicit Demand Response schemes	ER-07, AE-03
UC9	Participation in implicit Demand Response schemes	ER-07, AE-01, AE-02, AE-03
UC12	Optimal scheduling and operation of heating generation	ER-03, ER-04, ER-05, ER-08, MR-01
UC13	Increase self-consumption at local level	EC-03, ER-01, ER-02, ER-06
UC14	Active Citizen and LEC Engagement	AE-01, AE-02, AE-04, AE-06, BU-01, BU-02, BU-03

This table is a little different from the table in D6.7. The reason is that after the level 1 and level 2 audits which were conducted in late 2022, we found out only very few assets could be part of ACCEPT due to the fact that many assets are not known by the tech partners or could not be influenced by the ACCEPT solution. Therefore we discussed internally again which use cases were useful for us to explore and test. UC10 is not relevant anymore to reach our goals.

The formation of an energy community in the Netherlands aims to achieve several objectives that benefit the local community. One of the primary goals is to increase self-consumption of local PV electricity, which can lead to greater self-sufficiency and energy independence. By optimizing the use of locally generated renewable energy, the community can reduce its dependence on external sources of energy and decrease its carbon footprint, contributing to climate change mitigation efforts.

The Dutch pilot site is implementing a range of UCs that are intended to support the community's goals around DR and self-consumption. Each UC is tailored to address specific objectives and is linked to particular assets within the community. This information is summarized in Table 2, with each row containing the use case ID and name, the community objective assets related to the UC.

Table 2: objective per UC and assets concerned

ID	Name	Objective	Assets
UC1	Metering & Sensor Energy Data	To collect data on energy consumption and production from the assets to enable the other use cases	All assets equipped with meters for data collection
UC2	Virtual Energy Storage optimisation	To optimise the storage potential of the water tank and the whole heating system for demand flexibility	District heatpump
UC4	Demand elasticity profiling-forecasting-aggregation	To understand more about the possibility of using DR-schemes	All assets at the pilot site
UC5	Intra-day district-level DER flexibility management	To manage and optimise the use of PV electricity and controllable loads within the AIC district to meet energy demand and improve self-consumption	District heatpump
UC7	Community-level P2P flexibility	To understand better the possibility of P2P exchange of energy	Assets at household level
UC8	Participation in explicit Demand Response schemes	To learn if households want to participate	Assets at household level
UC9	Participation in implicit Demand Response schemes	To learn if households allow ACCEPT to intervene	Assets at household level
UC12	Optimal scheduling and operation of heating generation	To optimise the scheduling and operation of the district heating system to optimize the performance	District heatpump
UC13	Increase self-consumption at local level	To improve self-consumption of PV electricity and reduce reliance on the grid	All assets at the pilot site
UC14	Active Citizen and LEC Engagement	To engage with households to promote energy efficiency and demand response acceptance	All concerned at pilot site

Together with all partners the critical path for the testing was designed in March 2023. This resulted in a delay in testing of many UC's. Furthermore, in Holland no IoT equipment is yet installed. The reason for this, as explained in D6.7, is the delays in the installation and commissioning process. Currently, we wait for the BoM which is expected in April. Depending on the time of delivery of the equipment we hope to finish installation and commissioning at the end of June 2023. Due to the summer holidays, we expect it will not be possible to start testing before the end of August. So the planning of the demonstration activities is very difficult in this stage. We give a rough estimate as we see it at this moment. Maybe the testing of UC4, 12, 13, and 14 might become critical because it's not clear yet when the tools will be available.

Table 3: planning demonstration activities

ID	Name	IoT working	Start of demonstration
UC1	Metering & Sensor Energy Data	June 2023	September 2023
UC2	Virtual Energy Storage optimisation	September 2023	October 2023 with the next heating season
UC4	Demand elasticity profiling-forecasting-aggregation	June 2023	September 2023
UC5	Intra-day district-level DER flexibility management	August 2023 (M32)	October 2023 with the next heating season
UC7	Community-level P2P flexibility	June 2023	September 2023
UC8	Participation in explicit Demand Response schemes	June 2023	September 2023
UC9	Participation in implicit Demand Response schemes	June 2023	September 2023
UC12	Optimal scheduling and operation of heating generation	June 2023	October 2023 with the next heating season
UC13	Increase self-consumption at local level	June 2023	September 2023
UC14	Active Citizen and LEC Engagement		September 2023

Households in the pilot site are very much engaged in the project. We have a special group for testing the c-app and many people visit meetings. We intend to organize again a new meeting before the installation of the IoT-equipment as smart meters and also when testing actually starts.

At another level, we made a special offer to households in order to install home battery systems and smart switches. Though this equipment is not always direct interesting for ACCEPT, it surely will help the households to stay engaged.

Since only a few appliances are part of ACCEPT, there is no reason to do health monitoring. ACCEPT will not influence the health in the cooperating houses.

3. Preparation of the Pilot Test-Bed

In Holland, the installation of IoT-equipment is delayed. As mentioned before we expect to start testing after the summer holidays. In Table 4 we show how we intend to test the UCs.

Table 4: how UCs will be tested

ID	Name	Assets	How the UC will be tested
UC1	Metering & Sensor Energy Data	All assets equipped with meters for data collection	The data will be monitored, and its accuracy evaluated.
UC2	Virtual Energy Storage optimisation	District heatpump	The storage and the whole heating system will be monitored to model their consumption.
UC4	Demand elasticity profiling-forecasting-aggregation	All assets at the pilot site	The assets will be monitored to identify patterns in energy usage and demand. The data will be analysed to forecast consumer demand-side flexibility, which will be used to optimize the energy system's overall performance.
UC5	Intra-day district-level DER flexibility management	District heatpump	The district assets will be monitored in real-time, and their flexibility will be forecasted and optimized to balance energy demand and supply.
UC7	Community-level P2P flexibility	Assets at household level	Agregated demand and production will be monitored to check possibilities for P2P flexibility
UC8	Participation in explicit Demand Response schemes	Assets at household level	Monitoring how many households interact with explicit DR-requests
UC9	Participation in implicit Demand Response schemes	Assets at household level	Monitoring how many households overrule implicit DR-requests
UC12	Optimal scheduling and operation of heating generation	District heatpump	Monitoring if proposed adaption of the heat pump is followed up by the manager of the heat pump
UC13	Increase self-consumption at local level	All assets at the pilot site	The energy generated by the PV plants will be used to increase local self-consumption, and the system's performance will be monitored to evaluate its effectiveness in increasing self-consumption.
UC14	Active Citizen and LEC Engagement	All concerned at pilot site	The feedback of the participants will be collected through questionnaires, surveys or workshops.

4. Support activities

Even before the installation and commissioning of the IoT-equipment, we have formed a group of local heroes who form the installation team. They will be trained by Hypertech and are also afterward available for all kind of support activities. People at the pilot site know these people and therefore can reach them easily by phone or direct contact. All technicians live in the pilot site. This way the support activities don't need to be formalised in activities to be planned.

5. Local4Local

To stress the importance of ACCEPT for the Netherlands, in 2022 we started the project Local4Local. With a subsidy of the Dutch government of € 4,6 mln for the years 2023-2026 and investment by the Dutch cooperatives of € 3,2 mln. The objective of Local4Local is to develop and implement a cooperative model for an integrated, sustainable, collective energy supply (the local4local model), in which the end user does not pay more than what we call "cost price +", with a minimized impact on the local energy infrastructure.

By cost price+ we mean: the full charged price of generating, purchasing, distributing, storing, sharing, and supplying renewable energy, deducted from the income from flexibility markets and the sale of surpluses of renewable electricity or heat. Included in the costs are: financing costs including interest, personnel costs, material costs and research costs. The 'plus' includes, among other things: reservations for future investments, the absorption of risks and investments in social goals.

The basics of Local4Local can be found in Figure 1. The Figure shows the priority to use locally produced energy for local use or local storage. Only when the local production and use/storage is not in balance, the grid will be used for (return)delivery of electricity.

Figure 1: basics of Local4Local concept

6. Next Steps

The first steps are to work on the BoM, procurement, installation and commissioning of the IoT-equipment. In June we expect this to be ready.

When the installation and commissioning phase is completed for each asset and demonstration can begin according to the timeline presented before. The advancement of the demonstration activities will be reported in D7.14 – demonstration activity report from the Dutch pilot site.